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A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND TEAM EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence plays an important role in improving effectiveness of team. Paper examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and effectiveness of 15 teams of Law professionals from Gwalior. A single questionnaire was used to gather data from the teams, each team consisting of 5-15 members. Co-relation was applied to investigate the relationships between emotional intelligence as a whole and team effectiveness. Results indicated that emotional intelligence had positive impact on team effectiveness. The study recommended that experimental study may be conducted to compare the effectiveness of teams before and after providing the training on emotional intelligence so that a clear picture may emerge.

Key words: Emotional intelligence, team effectiveness,

Introduction:

The concept of emotional intelligence (EI) was first proposed by Mayer & Salovey (1990) which was then popularized by Goleman. EI came up from the work of social intelligence by Thorndike (1920) & Gardner's (1983) concept of intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence. In 1927, Thorndike classified Intelligence into three types: Abstract Intelligence which is related to verbal concepts, Concrete Intelligence which is related to shapes and matter and thirdly Social Intelligence now termed as Emotional Intelligence. It shows that it is not a new concept. The researchers have defined EI as a distinct psychological skill that can be consistently gauged. Salovey & Mayer (1990) defined emotional intelligence as the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions. Their model includes features of intelligence, adjustability and encouragement.

Almost everyone would agree that it is good to possess street smarts and social intelligence. People, who can detect emotions in others, control their own emotions and handle social interactions well will have a powerful leg up in the business world.

Dimensions of Emotional Intelligence:

Emotional intelligence comprises four abilities, self-emotion appraisal, and emotion appraisal of others, use of emotion and regulation of emotion (Wong & Law, 2002).

Appraisal of Self and Others Emotion. The first factor of EI is the ability to properly determine and express one's own emotions as well as to be sympathetic, appraise and express emotions of others.

Every individual's ability varies in precisely identifying, appraising and expressing his own emotions as well as the emotions experienced by others. Some people are attentive of their feelings they experience and can express their emotions whereas, some people cannot express their feelings and emotions or they are unaware of their emotions (Zhou, George, 2003).

The research indicated that there is a positive relationship between job performance and team members having high EI because they are highly proficient at appraising and regulating their own emotions which results in a higher level of faith in themselves and have power over them which lead them to make realistic actions resulting in high performance and less supervisory interference. But where team members have low EI, they are less proficient at appraising and regulating their emotions, so they have to get assistance from their managers in helping them to better manage and control their emotions which lead to teamwork, coordination, creativity and adaptability (Sy, Tram, O'Hara, 2006).

Use of Emotions. Another factor includes the ability of the individual to use emotions to aid the cognitive processes. Emotions and cognitions are highly interconnected and EI allows people with the ability to use emotions to aid the effective cognitive processing of information. Emotions can be used to emphasize on important matters like selecting among competing and similar options, increase the flexibility of information processing, and engage in certain kinds of information processing. Therefore, individuals vary not only in awareness, appraisal and expression of emotions but also in their ability to use emotions in collaboration with their cognitive processes to enhance effective functioning. For adjusting in changing situations, emotions play an important role in the effective development of information for the individuals who are high on EI. On the contrary, individuals with low EI cannot effectively use their emotions to aid cognitive processes and may find it difficult to coordinate among how they feel and what are they doing (Zhou, George, 2003).

Regulation of Emotions. The fourth element of EI is about the regulation of emotions of the people. People not only understand the emotions of others but also make an effort to manage these emotions. Some individuals are much competent in managing emotional management process for themselves as well as for other, as compared to other people. For example, if there occur any breach in quality, it may raise up a negative emotional reaction when the manager tries to determine the reason of the problem i.e. anger. Though the manager, instead of being obsessed with blaming others and seeking revenge, s/he should manage his/her anger to effectively solve the problem. It is significantly important for leaders to manage the emotions of others. Emotional reactions provide a useful insight of where interest should be focused, whereas unmanaged emotions can hinder the effective information processing. So to avoid this unduly hindrance, EI allows managers to not only use emotions but also to manage them effectively (Zhou, George, 2003).

Mayer & Salovey (1997) also stated four skills of EI which includes emotional awareness of own and others, emotional management of own and others, emotional understanding and emotional facilitation. They also developed an inventory to measure emotional intelligence (Mayer, Salovey & Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test, 2002)

Goleman (1998) stated that emotional intelligence play a major role in improving performance at work as well as achievements in personal life. He claimed that approximately 90 % of the performance between high and average individuals at senior leader positions was due to emotional intelligence features rather than cognitive ones (Cha, Cichy & Kim, 2009).

Concept of Team:

Ayoko & Callan (2009) defined teams as groups composed of autonomous individuals who are wholly identified as team, having a shared liability and are together accountable for accomplishment of tasks identified by the organization. Teams are said to be necessary for organizational effectiveness. To extract maximum performance from team it requires the selection of people with suitable and adequate skills and knowledge who can understand and cater to team needs. Mostly required skills include emotional intelligence skill set because it accounts for eighty percent of success of an individual (Goleman, 1995). Researchers are now applying the concept of emotional intelligence to teamwork to help groups perform more effectively. Vanessa Druskat, one of the premier researchers on group emotional intelligence, has identified three emotional competencies that create group emotional intelligence: (1) awareness and regulation of individual group members' emotions, (2)

awareness and regulation of group-level emotion (3) awareness and regulation of emotion associated with cross-boundary activities. Individual and group emotional intelligence help build group trust, group identity, and efficacy, which research indicates are the three conditions essential to a groups effectiveness (Druskat and Wolff, 2001).

Relationship of Emotional Intelligence with Team Effectiveness:

As emotional intelligence is critical for effectiveness of performance, a person who knows how to stay motivated under stress, motivate others, manage complex interpersonal relationships, his/her others and build teams who are recognized specialists on a product or service are likely to get will get better results (Goleman, 2005). Emotional intelligence is a multi-dimensional concept that links emotion and cognition to improve human interactions. It has been linked to improved workplace behaviour and specifically team behaviour and team performance. (Jordan, Peter, Lawrence & Sandra, 2009). In recent research, it was found that team performance is positively and significantly influenced if team is able to recognize emotions of teammates (Stough, Saklofske & Parker, 2009).

Though there are many claims regarding the positive impact of emotional intelligence on job performance, but the studies examining the relationship between emotional intelligence and individual level performance show that the perceived potential benefits of using emotional intelligence in the workplace may be absent.

Jordan & Troth (2004) have found a link between emotional intelligence and performance on a purely cognitive task at group level, although this relationship did not appear at individual level. Further, Sy, Tram & O'Hara(2006) found that employees having high emotional intelligence are more skilled to regulate their own as well as manage others' emotions to promote positive interactions which would lead to higher performance through organizational citizenship behavior. Similarly, Weiss & Cropanzano (1996) revealed that managers having high emotional intelligence exhibit optimistic work attitudes and unselfish behaviors which resultantly lead to employees' higher satisfaction and performance at job. In majority of teams, the role of leadership is revolved so it is predicted that teams with emotional intelligence perform well (Jordan, Ashkanasy, Hartel & Hooper, 2002).

Research Methodology:

The study was relational for exploring relationship among Emotional Intelligence (EI), Self Emotion Appraisal (SEA), Other Emotion Appraisal (OEA), Using Emotions (UE) and Regulation of Emotions (RE). These variables were tested.

Sample Design

Sample Size - 15 work teams comprised of 5-15 members

Sampling Technique: Convenience sampling

Scope of Study: Study is limited to Law professional of Gwalior

Data Collection: Primary data collected from Law professional of Gwalior

Study Duration: July 2014

Tools for Data Collection:

Primary data was gathered through questionnaires. The questionnaire consisted of 42 items. The performance of team was measured by 16 items, adopted from Senior (1996). Emotional Intelligence was assessed using Wong & Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS, 2002). This scale also consisted of 16 items. The WLEIS was designed as a short measure of Emotional Intelligence for use in organizational research. It measures four dimensions: Self-Emotion Appraisal, Emotion Appraisal of Others, Use of Emotion, and Regulation of Emotion. All the items related to emotional intelligence as well as team effectiveness was measured on a 7-point likert scale (7 = Strongly Agree to 1 = Strongly Disagree).

Data Analysis and Results:

Data was collected from 15 different teams of Law professional of Gwalior. The data collected was analyzed using SPSS Version 18. By running reliability analysis to the data, Cronbach's Alpha value was found to be 0.835 which shows that instrument was 83% reliable as mentioned in table 1.

Table 1 - Reliability Statistics

Cronbach Alpha	No. of items
.83	42

Table 2 – Descriptive Statistics

N = 100	Mean	Standard Deviation
Emotional Intelligence	5.6	.90
Team Effectiveness	5.4	.87

Table 2 indicates that the mean score of emotional intelligence of the employees was 5.6 which mean that the teams had somewhat high level of correlation. Team effectiveness was also high.

Table 3. Inter-item correlation matrix

Variables	Self emotion appraisal	Others emotional appraisal	Use of emotion	Regulation of emotion	Team performance	Emotional Intelligence
Self emotion appraisal	1.0	.42	.60	.42	.54	.79
Others emotional appraisal	.42	1.0	.40	.34	.36	.70
Use of emotion	.60	.40	1.0	.43	.70	.80
Regulation of emotion	.42	.34	.43	1.0	.37	.75
Team performance	.56	.36	.70	.37	1.0	.65
Emotional Intelligence	.79	.70	.80	.75	.65	1.0

The above table shows that the self emotion appraisal and use of emotion are highly correlated with team performance, whereas other emotion appraisal and regulation of emotion were although positively correlated but having weak relationship with team performance.

Discussions:

The present study produced some important results having implications for both theory and practice. The result indicated that emotional intelligence had positive impact on team effectiveness which is in line with the findings of previous researches.

A particularly interesting finding of the present study was that high emotional intelligence work teams performed at a higher level than low emotional intelligence teams. This study has implications for managers, suggesting that organizations could profit by identification of high and low emotional intelligence work teams; so that interventions can be focused on the low emotional intelligence teams where maximum benefits can be realized.

Recommendations:

Since Emotional Intelligence proves to be a key contributing factor for effectiveness of team, organizations and managers take steps to become more emotionally intelligent to play their role in developing a more emotionally urbanized workforce. This can be done through introducing emotional learning programs in the organization on regular basis. This Emotional Intelligence training will be

helpful to individual employees and managers too. Similarly, by acquiring emotional intelligence skill set, manager may be able to communicate to employees in a better way.

Conclusion:

Sometimes, employees are engaged in positive as well as negative emotions, it is important for them to perceive, analyze their own emotions as well as of others, use them in an effective way, and regulate them in such a way that it provides them maximum benefit instead of harm. Emotional reactions provide a useful insight of where interest may be focused, whereas unmanaged emotions can hinder the effective information processing.

References:

- Cha, J., Cichy, R.F., & Kim, S.H. (2009). The contribution of emotional intelligence to social skills and stress management skills among automated foodservice industry executives. *In Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism, 8(1), 15-31*
- Goleman, D. (2005). *Emotional Intelligence*. (10th Ed). New York: Bantam Books.
- Jordan, P. J., Ashkanasy, N. M., Härtel, C. E. J., & Hooper, G. S. (2002). Workgroup emotional intelligence: Scale development and relationship to team process effectiveness and goal focus. *In Human Resource Management Review, 12(2), 195-214*.
- Jordan, P.J., Lawrence, S, A. (2009). Emotional intelligence in teams: Development and initial validation of the short version of the Workgroup Emotional Intelligence Profile (WEIP-S). *In journal of Management and Organization*.
- Mayer, J., & Salovey, P. (1990). Emotional intelligence and the construction and regulation of feelings. *Applied and Preventative Psychology, 4, 197-208*.
- Mayer, J., D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P.Salovey and D. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional Development and Emotional Intelligence: Implications for the Educator*. New York Basic Books.
- Salovey, P. & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *In Imagination, Cognition and Personality, 9, 185-211*. Retrieved April 02, 2010
- Stough, C., Saklofske, D. H., & Parker, J. D. (2009) *Assessing Emotional Intelligence: Theory, Research, and Applications*.
- Sy, T., Tram, S., and O'Hara, L. A. (2006). Relation of employee and manger emotional intelligence to job satisfaction and performance. *In Journal of Vocational Behavior, 68, 461-473*.
- Thorndike, E.L. (1920). Intelligence and its uses. *Harper's Magazine, 140, 227-235*.
- Weiss, H., & Cropanzano, R. (1996). Affective events theory: a theoretical discussion of the structure, causes and consequences of affective experiences at work. *In Research in Organizational Behavior, 18, 1-79*.
- Wong, C., Law, K. S. (2002). The effects of leader and follower emotional intelligence on performance and attitude: An exploratory study. *Leadership Quarterly, 13(3), 243-274*.
- Zainab Naseer etal(2011).Impact of emotional intelligence on team performance in higher education institutes. *International online journal of educational sciences,2011,3(1),30-46*
- Zhou, J., George, J. M. (2003). Awakening employee creativity: The role of leader emotional intelligence. *Leadership Quarterly, 14, 545 - 568*.